

Efforts to identify the *Agaricus campestris*-like species on urban lawns in Guangzhou City (South China)

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Text

"*Agaricus campestris* (L. 1753)" is so well-known a name in Chinese mycological circle that no one interested in this field would miss it. However, unfortunately this species does not seem to have a confirmed presence in China as suggested by recent molecular studies on related groups (e.g., Liu *et al.* 2020, Yang *et al.* 2025). Having been curious on the *Agaricus campestris*-like mushrooms frequently found on urban lawns across Guangzhou City for a long time, we launched an extensive collecting project focusing on this group from 2023 to 2025 (actually mainly in 2025 :), yielded 39 collections, got them all sequenced with necessary loci (ITS, nrLSU, *rpb1*, *rpb2* and *tef-1a*), and finally unveiled two most common species showing here with details.

As present in figure 1, an ITS phylogeny can easily identify our collections into two distinct clade representing two species with significant support, namely *Agaricus andrewii* A.E. Freeman (1979, originally described from America) and the just published *A. cantonotraminus* Kun L. Yang, Jia Y. Lin & Zhu L. Yang (2025, type locality in Guangzhou City).

As present in figure 2, among these 39 collections, 16 are *A. andrewii* and 23 are *A. cantonotraminus*, implying that the latter is possibly more common than the former in Guangzhou City.

Notably, the easy identification of these two species is actually benefitted by ITS sequencing. Their macromorphologies are quite unfriendly for distinguishing. What's worse, in some extreme instances we found these species growing together (Figure 3).

It looks interesting that the protologue of *A. andrewii* describes this species as bearing cheilocystidia (Freeman 1979), a character contrary to the general character of *Agaricus* sect. *Agaricus* (and of course, also of *A. cantonotraminus*). In later stage, we may try to explore effective micromorphological differences between these two species based on our own collections.

▲ **Figure 1.** ITS phylogeny of *Agaricus campestris* complex, easily identified our collections into two distinct clade representing two species. However, the macromorphologies of these two species are unfriendly for identification.

▲ **Figure 2.** Distribution pattern of the 39 collections containing two species introduced in this poster in Guangzhou City.

▲ **Figure 3.** Two fairy rings, belonging to two naturally different (ITS sequenced) but macromorphologically indistinguishable species, found on the lawn near the Xinjiao Mid. Rd.—Guangzhou Ave. S. Tunnel on March 9, 2025.

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